

Risk Assessment Methodology

Document Owner: Information Security Manager
Approved By: Information Security Committee
Approval Date: 04/30/2026
Effective Date: 04/30/2026

© 2026 Juan Ruda

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19917605>

This publication is distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

License details: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Revision History

Version	Date	Created By	Description of Changes
1.0	03/15/2026	Stephan Krauss (ISM)	Initial report

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	4
2. Risk Assessment.....	4
2.1. Risk Identification	4
Step #1: Identification of the asset	4
Step #2: Identification of threats.....	5
Step # 3: Identification of vulnerabilities	5
Step # 4: Identification of current controls.....	7
Step # 5: Mapping of threat-vulnerability to current controls	9
2.2. Risk Analysis.....	11
Step # 6: Impact Analysis.....	11
Step # 7: Likelihood Analysis	14
Step # 8: Analysis of Level of Risk	15
2.3. Risk Evaluation	16
Step # 9: Evaluate Risk.....	16
Step # 10: Risk Treatment Suggestions.....	17
3. Conclusion.....	18

1. Introduction

This document presents a sample risk assessment applied to a single organizational asset. It is conducted step by step, with brief explanations of the reasoning behind each stage to demonstrate the methodology in practice and the level of granularity expected.

The focus on one asset is intentional, allowing clear illustration of the approach. A full company-wide assessment would require dedicated tools and cross-functional collaboration. While the methodology itself is sound and scalable, the tools used in this sample are illustrative only.

This example is intended to demonstrate the practicality and logic of the proposed risk assessment methodology.

2. Risk Assessment

2.1. Risk Identification

Step # 1: Identification of the asset

The asset selected for this sample is the Amazon Web Services (AWS) Production Account. This is a critical asset, as it serves as the control plane for the organization's entire cloud environment and forms the foundation for all production services.

Asset Register Entry

ID	AST-03
Name	AWS Production Account
Criticality	Very High
Description	Cloud Hosting Platform Account. Central cloud tenant hosting infrastructure resources.
Category	Service
Location	Cloud Provider Region
Owner	Infrastructure & DevOps Lead
Dependencies	NULL

Step # 2: Identification of threats

During this step, threats to the asset are identified. This methodology uses the threat list provided in ISO 27005 Annex C as a reference. Because the standard’s threat descriptions are intentionally broad, the first column adapts the naming to make it more specific and relevant to a cloud service environment.

In practice, the number of potential threats that could target an asset is virtually unlimited. Therefore, the focus is placed on reasonably foreseeable and relevant threats, described in a sufficiently generic way to capture different variations within the same threat category.

The third column identifies the origin of the threat: **D** (Deliberate) **A** (Accidental) **E** (Environmental).

Finally, a column indicates whether each threat impacts confidentiality, integrity, availability, or a combination of these.

Threat Identification Table

Threat Source	Standard Name (ISO 27005)	Origin	C	I	A
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account	Unauthorized use of equipment	D	X	X	X
Misconfiguration or accidental deletion of AWS resources	Error in use	A		X	X
Misuse of privileged IAM	Abuse of rights	A D	X	X	X
Privilege escalation within IAM	Forging of rights	D	X	X	X
Unavailability of DevOps personnel	Breach of personnel availability	A D E			X
AWS service resource or limit exhaustion	Saturation of the information system	A D			X

Step # 3: Identification of vulnerabilities

During this step, vulnerabilities that could reasonably and foreseeably be exploited by each identified threat are documented. At this stage, existing controls are intentionally disregarded. The objective is to assess the inherent weaknesses of the asset so we can later determine whether current controls are sufficient, appropriate, or excessive.

Evaluating the situation before considering safeguards helps clarify why certain controls exist, or whether they meaningfully contribute to information security at all.

The third column indicates the vulnerability category, using ISO 27005 Annex D as a reference.

This step also illustrates the multiplicative effect of the asset-based approach: a single asset may be exposed to multiple threats, and each threat may exploit multiple vulnerabilities, significantly expanding the overall risk landscape.

Vulnerability Identification Table

Threat	Vulnerability	Type
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account	Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms	Software
	Poor password management	Software
	Lack of formal procedure for user registration and de-registration	Organization
Misconfiguration or accidental deletion of AWS resources	Incorrect parameter set up	Software
	Lack of effective change control	Software
	Insufficient security training	Personnel
Misuse of privileged IAM	Wrong allocation of access rights	Software
	Lack of audit trail	Software
	Lack of formal process for access right review	Organization
Privilege escalation within IAM	Lack of formal process for access right review	Organization
	Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms	Software
	Wrong allocation of access rights	Software
Unavailability of DevOps personnel	Absence of personnel	Personnel
	Lack of continuity plans	Organization
AWS service resource or limit exhaustion	Lack of procedure of monitoring of information processing facilities	Organization
	Lack of continuity plans	Organization

Step # 4: Identification of current controls

At this stage, the existing controls are identified. For this sample, controls were selected based on what an organization of similar size and maturity would reasonably have implemented for this asset.

The maturity level was also assessed of each control using the following reference scale:

#	Level	Description
0	Nonexistent	There is a total absence of identifiable processes
1	Initial	Processes are implemented case by case without any method
2	Managed	Nonstandard processes are in place
3	Defined	Processes are documented and communicated
4	Quantitatively managed	Processes are monitored and measured
5	Optimized	Processes are optimized

Most identified controls are at Level 3 (Defined), meaning procedures and training exist, but implementation may still vary in practice. Two controls were assessed at Level 2 (Managed), indicating a need for further formalization to ensure consistency and reliability.

Additionally, each control was classified by type: P (Preventive), D (Detective), C (Corrective).

Finally, each control was mapped to the security objective(s) it supports, confidentiality, integrity, and/or availability.

Control Identification Table

Control	Description	Level of Maturity	Type	C	I	A
AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	Access to the AWS production account is granted through individual IAM accounts with role-based permissions aligned to job functions. The access model is documented and communicated to relevant personnel. However, access reviews are not formally measured for effectiveness.	3 – Defined	P	X	X	
Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) for	MFA is enforced for privileged and administrative accounts. The requirement is formally established and	3 – Defined	P	X	X	

privileged accounts	communicated to personnel as part of secure access practices. There is no quantitative measurement of MFA effectiveness beyond enforcement.					
CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	CloudTrail is enabled across the production account and logs are retained according to documented procedures. Logging requirements are documented and communicated, but systematic monitoring metrics and KPIs are not formally measured.	3 – Defined	D	X	X	
Formal change management process	Production changes require ticket submission and peer approval following a documented procedure communicated to technical staff. While standardized, the organization does not quantitatively measure change success rates or procedural compliance.	3 – Defined	P D		X	X
Backup & automated snapshots	Automated backups are configured for critical production resources following a documented backup procedure. Recovery responsibilities are communicated; however, restoration testing is not systematically measured or optimized.	3 – Defined	C		X	X
CloudWatch monitoring & quota alerts	Monitoring and alerting follow a consistent technical configuration across production systems. However, there are no formal training sessions or documented performance metrics to evaluate monitoring effectiveness. Personnel rely on operational knowledge to respond to alerts.	2 – Managed	D		X	X
Business Continuity Plan (BCP)	A documented continuity plan exists describing roles and recovery priorities. While implemented using a consistent approach, training sessions and formal testing are limited, and personnel rely partially on experience during incidents.	2 – Managed	C	X	X	X

Step # 5: Mapping of threat-vulnerability to current controls

During this step, controls are identified that help reduce either the likelihood of a threat exploiting a vulnerability or the potential impact if such exploitation occurs.

Threat + Vulnerability	Controls	Reduces Impact	Reduces Likelihood
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms	AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	N	Y
	Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) for privileged accounts	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> Poor password management	Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) for privileged accounts	N	Y
	AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> Lack of formal procedure for user registration and de-registration	AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	N	Y
	Formal change management process	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
Misconfiguration or accidental deletion of AWS resources <i>due to</i> Incorrect parameter set up	Formal change management process	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
	Backup & automated snapshots	Y	N
	Business Continuity Plan	Y	N
Misconfiguration or accidental deletion of AWS resources <i>due to</i> Lack of effective change control	Formal change management process	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
	Backup & automated snapshots	Y	N
Misconfiguration or accidental deletion of AWS resources <i>due to</i> Insufficient security training	There is no formal security awareness or technical training program.	N	N

Misuse of privileged IAM <i>due to</i> Wrong allocation of access rights	AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	N	Y
	Multi-Factor Authentication	N	Y
	Formal change management process	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
Misuse of privileged IAM <i>due to</i> Lack of audit trail	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
Misuse of privileged IAM <i>due to</i> Lack of formal process for access right review	There is no formal periodic access review process	N	N
Privilege escalation within IAM <i>due to</i> Lack of formal process for access right review	There is no formal periodic access review process	N	N
Privilege escalation within IAM <i>due to</i> Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms	AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	N	Y
	Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) for privileged accounts	N	Y
Privilege escalation within IAM <i>due to</i> Wrong allocation of access rights	AWS IAM with unique user accounts with RBAC	N	Y
	Formal change management process	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
Unavailability of DevOps personnel <i>due to</i> Absence of personnel	Business Continuity Plan (BCP)	Y	N
Unavailability of DevOps personnel <i>due to</i> Lack of continuity plans	Business Continuity Plan (BCP)	Y	N
AWS service resource or limit exhaustion <i>due to</i> Lack of procedure of monitoring of information processing facilities	CloudWatch monitoring & quota alerts	N	Y
	CloudTrail logging enabled and retained	Y	N
AWS service resource or limit exhaustion <i>due to</i> Lack of continuity plans	Business Continuity Plan (BCP)	Y	N
	Backup & automated snapshots	Y	N

2.2. Risk Analysis

Step # 6: Impact Analysis

During this step, the impact of a threat exploiting a vulnerability is analyzed across confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Each component of the CIA triad is assessed separately, resulting in three distinct impact evaluations per risk scenario.

Impact is measured in financial terms to ensure objectivity and consistency. The following scale is used:

#	Level	Financial Range	Description
1	Insignificant	< \$50,000	Minor incident, absorbed operationally
2	Minor	\$50,000 – \$250,000	Noticeable but no strategic effect
3	Significant	\$250,000 – \$1,000,000	Management-level issue, affects profit
4	Severe	\$1,000,000 – \$2,500,000	Board-level concern, valuation impact
5	Catastrophic	> \$2,500,000	Strategic threat, growth or funding impact

To ensure sufficient granularity and a structured assessment, each component of the CIA triad is further analyzed across three impact dimensions: Business, Legal/Regulatory, and Contractual.

The following reference categories are used to guide the evaluation:

Business impact	Legal/Regulatory impact	Contractual impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenue Loss Operational Disruption Incident Response & Technical Recovery Cost Reputational Damage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory enforcement Legally Mandatory Compliance Costs Legal Defense & Settlements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLA Penalties Indemnification Obligations

The risk chosen for this demonstration is: Unauthorized access to AWS Production account *due to* weak identification and authentication mechanisms, *leading to* compromise of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information.

This risk was selected for the demonstration because it represents a high-impact and realistic scenario for a cloud-based organization. The AWS Production Account serves as the control plane of the entire cloud environment; therefore, weaknesses in identification and authentication mechanisms could lead to full administrative compromise. Additionally, this risk clearly affects all three elements of the CIA triad.

Impact to confidentiality Scenario: Unauthorized access to AWS Production account *due to* Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms *as a result* Attacker gains administrative access and is able to exfiltrate customer data (law firm client data).

Business impact	Legal/Regulatory Impact	Contractual Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenue Loss \$400K – \$1.5M Operational Disruption \$75K – \$250K Incident Response & Technical Recovery Cost \$250K – \$900K Reputational Damage \$1.0M – \$3.5M 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory enforcement \$100K – \$750K Legally Mandatory Compliance Costs \$75K – \$250K Legal Defense & Settlements \$250K – \$1.5M 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLA Penalties \$75K – \$300K Indemnification Obligations \$250K – \$1.2M

Impact to integrity scenario: Unauthorized access to AWS Production account *due to* Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms *as a result* Attacker modifies, corrupts, or manipulates production data or configurations.

Business impact	Legal/Regulatory Impact	Contractual Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenue Loss \$200K – \$1.5M Operational Disruption \$150K – \$500K Incident Response & Technical Recovery Cost \$350K – \$900K Reputational Damage \$1.1M – 4.5 M 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory enforcement \$150K – \$1.0M Legally Mandatory Compliance Costs \$150K – \$400K Legal Defense & Settlements \$500K – \$2.5M 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLA Penalties \$50K – \$600K Indemnification Obligations \$600K – \$2.5M

Impact to availability scenario: Unauthorized access to AWS Production account *due to* Lack of identification and authentication mechanisms *as a result* Attacker causes service outage, deletes infrastructure, encrypts systems, or disrupts production environment.

Business impact	Legal/Regulatory Impact	Contractual Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenue Loss \$350K – \$1.5M Operational Disruption \$200K – \$600K Incident Response & Technical Recovery Cost \$400K – \$1.2M Reputational Damage \$1.1M – \$4.5M 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory enforcement \$0 – \$300K Legally Mandatory Compliance Costs \$75K – \$250K Legal Defense & Settlements \$250K – \$1.2M 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SLA Penalties \$200K – \$800K Indemnification Obligations \$300K – \$1.5M

After assessing the impact across confidentiality, integrity, and availability, and further analyzing each through the business, legal/regulatory, and contractual lenses, it was determined that, even at the lower end of the estimated range, the financial impact in most cases exceeds \$2.5 million. This places the impact level in the Catastrophic category across the board.

This outcome is consistent with the critical nature of the asset under analysis. The AWS Production Account functions as the core control plane of the organization’s cloud environment and provides access to all underlying cloud resources. A compromise at this level would have systemic consequences, justifying the severity of the impact assessment.

Impact Identification Table

Risk Scenario	Impact to Confidentiality			Impact to Integrity			Impact to Availability		
	B	L	C	B	L	C	B	L	C
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> weak identification and authentication mechanisms, <i>leading to</i> compromise of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information.	Catastrophic [5] (\$2.4M – \$9.6M)			Catastrophic [5] (\$3.2M – \$14.4M)			Catastrophic [5] (\$2.8M – \$11.8M)		
	1.7M – 7.1M	425K – 1.0M	325K – 1.5M	1.8M – 7.4M	800K – 3.9M	650K – 3.1M	2M – 7.8M	325K – 1.7M	500K – 2.3M

Step # 7: Likelihood Analysis

This step is about analyzing the likelihood of the threat exploiting the vulnerability successfully, likelihood is defined as follows:

$$\text{Likelihood} = \text{Frequency of threat occurring} \times \text{Probability of vulnerability being exploited}$$

For this purpose, the approach used relies on a percentage-based scale that estimates the probability of successful exploitation within a defined 12-month timeframe. The one-year horizon was selected because risk assessments are typically reviewed annually, and budgeting as well as control improvement planning are generally performed on a yearly cycle.

Additionally, the proposed percentage ranges serve as calibration anchors rather than statistical requirements. These ranges are intended to help differentiate between qualitative terms such as “possible” and “likely,” thereby improving consistency, clarity, and repeatability in the likelihood assessment process.

Likelihood Rating Scale

#	Level	Probability	Description
1	Rare	<5% chance within 12 months	Successful exploitation is highly unlikely under current controls and threat conditions. Would require exceptional circumstances.
2	Unlikely	5-15% chance within 12 months	Exploitation is possible but not expected under normal operating conditions.
3	Possible	15-40% chance within 12 months	Exploitation could reasonably occur given exposure and control maturity.
4	Likely	40-70% chance within 12 months	Exploitation is expected to occur under current conditions.
5	Almost Certain	>70% chance within 12 months	Exploitation is highly probable and may occur more than once if not addressed.

The resulting likelihood level is **Unlikely [2]**, primarily due to the existing identity and access management (IAM) and role-based access control (RBAC) controls currently in place.

While the scenario was close to being assessed as Rare, the controls are implemented at a Defined (Level 3) maturity stage. Although procedures are standardized and formally documented, their effectiveness is not yet quantitatively measured or optimized. Additionally, their application may vary across individual initiatives, leaving some margin for human error or inconsistent execution.

Risk Likelihood Analysis Summary

Risk	Likelihood Level	Justification
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> weak identification and authentication mechanisms, <i>leading to</i> compromise of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information.	Unlikely [2]	Exploitation is possible but not expected under normal operating conditions due to enforced IAM role-based access and MFA for privileged accounts. However, absence of formal effectiveness metrics, periodic access validation, and advanced monitoring prevents classification as Rare.

Step # 8: Analysis of Level of Risk

Finally, the assessed impact and likelihood levels are combined to determine the overall risk rating using the matrix below:

Risk Rating Matrix

5 →	Low (5)	Moderate (10)	High (15)	Very High (20)	Very High (25)
4 →	Very Low (4)	Low (8)	Moderate (12)	High (16)	Very High (20)
3 →	Very Low (3)	Low (6)	Moderate (9)	Moderate (12)	High (15)
2 →	Very Low (2)	Very Low (4)	Low (6)	Low (8)	Moderate (10)
1 →	Very Low (1)	Very Low (2)	Very Low (3)	Very Low (4)	Low (5)
Likelihood ↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
Impact →	1	2	3	4	5

Since the impact assessment for confidentiality, integrity, and availability was determined to be **Catastrophic [5]**, the overall impact value used is 5. For simplification purposes, a single impact value is applied; however, if different impact levels had been assigned to any element of the CIA triad, separate risk calculations would have been required.

The likelihood was assessed as **Unlikely [2]**. Applying the risk rating matrix methodology (Impact × Likelihood), the calculation is: **5 × 2 = 10**

This results in a final risk level of **Moderate [10]**.

Risk Level Analysis Summary

Risk	Impact	Likelihood	Risk Level
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> weak identification and authentication mechanisms, <i>leading to</i> compromise of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information.	Catastrophic [5]	Unlikely [2]	Moderate [10]

2.3. Risk Evaluation

Step # 9: Evaluate Risk

Now the risk level is compared against the risk acceptance criteria approved by the organization.

Risk Acceptance Criteria Matrix

Risk Level	Response	Management Action
Very Low	Accept	No additional action required. Maintain existing controls. Review during periodic risk reassessment.
Low	Accept	Acceptable risk. No immediate treatment required. Monitor through normal governance processes.

Moderate	Accept & Monitor	Risk owner must monitor. Identify cost-effective improvements to reduce risk to Low or Very Low where feasible. Management awareness required.
High	Treat	Risk treatment plan required. Controls must be implemented within defined timeframe. Management approval and tracking required.
Very High	Treat	Immediate action required. Senior management involvement mandatory. Risk cannot be accepted without formal executive approval.

Risk Evaluation Summary

Risk	Risk Level	Risk Acceptability
Unauthorized access to AWS Production account <i>due to</i> weak identification and authentication mechanisms, <i>leading to</i> compromise of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information.	Moderate [10]	Accept & Monitor

Step # 10: Risk Treatment Suggestions

Finally, since the risk was assessed as Moderate, the organization proposes the following cost-effective measures to further reduce the risk level.

To further reduce the likelihood of unauthorized access:

- Enforce Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) for all IAM users.
- Remove long-term access keys and adopt temporary security credentials.
- Apply conditional IP restrictions for AWS Management Console access.
- Conduct quarterly IAM access reviews to ensure least-privilege enforcement.

These measures are intended to strengthen identification and authentication controls and reduce the probability of unauthorized access to the AWS Production account.

The proposed measures will be reviewed by management to determine feasibility and implementation priority. Once approved, selected controls will be incorporated into the Risk Treatment Plan.

3. Conclusion

This demonstration illustrated how the organization's risk assessment methodology enables structured, repeatable, and financially grounded risk evaluations aligned with the principles of ISO 27001 and ISO 27005.

Although applied here to a single high-value asset, the methodology is designed to scale across the organization's full asset inventory and threat landscape.

The approach supports risk-based decision-making, consistent application of risk acceptance criteria, and ongoing improvement of the Information Security Management System (ISMS).